

Public knowledge, interest, and perception of chronic kidney disease educational content in Indonesia: a cross-sectional survey

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Received 18 September 2025 ♦ Accepted 5 January 2026 ♦ Published 9 February 2026

Citation: Zaim S, Bahar MuhA, Muzakkir AR, Anggriani A, Sarifah LM, Ibrahim N, Djabir YY (2026) Public knowledge, interest, and perception of chronic kidney disease educational content in Indonesia: a cross-sectional survey. *Pharmacia* 73: 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e172489>

Abstract

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) poses an increasing public health challenge in Indonesia, yet limited data exist on public knowledge, content preferences, and perceptions of existing CKD information. This study aimed to assess the public's knowledge regarding CKD, identify key areas of interest and preferred delivery formats, and evaluate perceptions toward current CKD educational materials among the Indonesian population. A cross-sectional survey-based study was conducted from November 2024 to January 2025. Among 651 respondents, 24.0% demonstrated good CKD knowledge, while 33.2% and 42.9% had moderate and poor knowledge, respectively. Female gender, single marital status, higher education, and employment in the health sector were significant factors that influenced knowledge levels ($p < 0.0001$). Public awareness of CKD in Indonesia remains inadequate, with knowledge levels strongly influenced by education, gender, and professional background. Tailoring educational content and delivery to align with public preferences may enhance engagement and support national efforts in CKD prevention.

Keywords

Chronic kidney disease, educational content, Indonesia, knowledge, public preference

Introduction

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a progressive and irreversible condition that poses a significant global health challenge due to its rising prevalence and substantial burden on healthcare systems. Often asymptomatic in its early stages, CKD frequently progresses unnoticed until

it reaches end-stage renal disease (ESRD), necessitating lifelong dialysis or kidney transplantation (Assiry et al. 2022). Approximately 10% of the global population is estimated to be affected by CKD, with prevalence steadily increasing, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (Kovesdy 2022). In the United States alone, over 37 million adults were living with CKD as of 2023 (CDC

2023), highlighting the magnitude of this condition even in high-resource settings.

Indonesia has experienced a comparable increase in CKD prevalence, rising from 2.0% in 2013 to 3.8% in 2018, affecting an estimated 12.5 million individuals (Health Research and Development Agency 2018). Multiple factors contribute to this growing burden, including diabetes mellitus, hypertension, obesity, advanced age, male gender, smoking, and consumption of energy supplements (Fadlilah et al. 2023). The financial impact is also substantial. In 2019, the National Health Insurance Agency reported 1.93 million CKD cases, incurring healthcare costs of IDR 2.79 trillion, which remained high during the 2020 COVID-19 pandemic despite a slight decrease in cases (MHRI 2023).

Despite its clinical and economic significance, CKD often remains undiagnosed until advanced stages, limiting opportunities for early intervention. Timely detection and management, especially among high-risk groups, have been shown to slow disease progression, enhance quality of life, and reduce long-term healthcare costs (Alobaidi 2021). However, early detection and prevention rely heavily on public health literacy and awareness. Individuals with limited understanding of CKD may fail to recognize early warning signs, neglect recommended lifestyle modifications, or delay seeking medical care, which leads to poorer clinical outcomes (Levin-Zamir and Bertschi 2018; Billany et al. 2023).

In Indonesia, public awareness of CKD varies by region, with higher levels reported in Bali and lower levels in Jogjakarta and Southeast Sulawesi (Kristina et al. 2020; Wulandar et al. 2020; Dharmapatni and Putri 2023). To address this issue, the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia (MHRI) has launched CKD-related educational initiatives through official digital platforms to enhance health literacy nationwide (MHRI 2021). While these efforts hold promise for increasing public engagement, their overall effectiveness has yet to be systematically assessed.

This study aimed to conduct a comprehensive, nationwide assessment of the Indonesian public's understanding of CKD and their engagement with the MHRI digital health content. By identifying key knowledge gaps, content and media preferences, as well as perceptions of existing educational materials, the findings are expected to provide important evidence to inform more effective health communication strategies and support efforts to reduce the growing burden of CKD in Indonesia.

Methods

Study design and population

A cross-sectional survey was conducted to assess public knowledge, interests, preferred media, and perceptions regarding CKD information in Indonesia. A structured,

pretested, and validated questionnaire was distributed online to maximize accessibility. Data collection took place from November 2024 to January 2025. Eligible participants were Indonesian citizens aged ≥ 18 years, able to read and understand Bahasa Indonesia, and willing to provide electronic consent and complete the online questionnaire independently. Respondents with incomplete submissions were excluded.

Data collection

Data were obtained using a self-administered online questionnaire (Google Forms) distributed via convenience sampling. The survey link was disseminated through social media (Facebook and Instagram) and messaging platforms (WhatsApp and Telegram), as well as official digital channels of the Indonesian Pharmacists Association, to broaden geographic and demographic reach. The questionnaire ensured anonymity, with no personally identifiable information collected. Data were securely stored in encrypted files accessible only to the principal investigators, maintaining confidentiality and compliance with ethical standards for human subject research.

Instrument

The questionnaire was developed based on consensus from an expert panel consisting of one academician, one renal pharmacist, and one nephrologist. The expert panel validated 48 preliminary questions, of which 44 were selected, with a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.85, indicating strong reliability.

The final questionnaire consisted of four sections and 44 items:

- Sociodemographic characteristics (11 items).
- Knowledge of CKD and kidney health (25 items): covering kidney physiology, risk factors, symptoms, and screening. Each item allowed for "Yes," "No," or "Don't Know" responses, scored as 1 for correct and 0 for incorrect or "Don't Know" answers (Gheewala et al. 2018).
- Interest in CKD information (2 items): assessing preferred topics and delivery methods.
- Perception of existing educational materials (6 items): assessed using a 4-point Likert scale

Translation process

Forward translation from English to Bahasa Indonesia was independently conducted by two bilingual translators. The two versions were reconciled into a single draft, which was reviewed by the principal investigator and research supervisor for cultural and contextual appropriateness. Backward translation into English was subsequently performed by two different profes-

sional translators to ensure semantic and conceptual equivalence. Discrepancies between the original and back-translated versions were discussed and resolved by consensus (Andreucci et al. 2020).

Pilot study

A pilot study was conducted with 30 participants selected from the target population to assess the clarity, comprehension, and cultural relevance of the questionnaire items. Participants were asked to complete the survey and provide structured feedback regarding question wording, interpretability, and ease of response. Based on this feedback, minor revisions were made to improve item clarity, reduce ambiguity, and minimize potential measurement error. The pilot test also helped assess the average completion time and technical usability of the online survey format (Perneger et al. 2015).

Sample size

The minimum sample size was determined using Slovin's formula with a 5% margin of error, based on the estimated Indonesian adult population of 209,576,907 in 2024. This calculation yielded a minimum requirement of 400 participants. To account for incomplete or inconsistent responses, the target sample size was increased by 20%, resulting in a final target of 480 participants.

Data analysis

Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 26. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations) were used to summarize sociodemographic characteristics and survey responses. Knowledge scores were obtained by summing correct answers (1 point each; 0 for incorrect or "Don't know") across 25 questions and classified using Bloom's cut-off: Good (80–100%, 20–25), Moderate (60–79%, 15–19), and Poor (< 60%, < 15) (Mahmoud et al. 2023).

Associations between sociodemographic factors and CKD knowledge were tested using the chi-square test, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$. Perceptions of CKD educational materials were analyzed descriptively using a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 4 = strongly agree; 0 = Don't know). Frequencies (%) and mean scores (SD) were reported to identify trends.

Ethical considerations

Informed consent was obtained digitally prior to participation via an introductory consent form embedded in the first section of the online questionnaire. Only respondents who provided consent were allowed to proceed to the survey. Ethical approval was granted by the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Pharmacy, Hasanuddin University (Approval Number: 577/UN4.17/KEP/2024).

Results

Sociodemographic data

A total of 651 complete responses were analyzed after the removal of incomplete submissions. Respondents were diverse in terms of region, age group, education, and employment, with the majority aged 18–30 years and holding at least a bachelor's degree. These demographic characteristics are summarized in Table 1 and were included in subgroup analyses to contextualize variations in knowledge.

Table 1. The demography of participants.

Variable	Frequency (%)
Gender	
Male	215 (33)
Female	436 (67)
Marital status	
Single	382 (58.7)
Married	251 (38.5)
Divorced/widowed	18 (2.8)
Age	
18–30	417 (64.1)
30–50	191 (29.3)
> 50	43 (6.6)
State of residence	
Western part of Indonesia	197 (30.3)
Central part of Indonesia	299 (45.9)
Eastern part of Indonesia	155 (23.8)
Education	
Secondary education	131 (20.1)
Diploma/Bachelor's degree	423 (65.0)
Postgraduate degree	97 (14.9)
Occupation	
Unemployed	58 (8.9)
Student	179 (27.5)
Self-employed	33 (5.1)
Health Service	91 (14.0)
Employee in the government sector	239 (36.7)
Employee in the private sector	51 (7.8)
Health insurance	
Yes	446 (68.5)
No	205 (31.5)
Monthly income	
< Rp. 1.500.000 (Low)	253 (38.9)
Rp. 1.500.000–3.500.000 (Middle)	178 (27.3)
> Rp. 3.500.000 (High)	220 (33.8)
Medical condition	
None	555 (85.3)
Chronic disease	96 (14.7)
Family history of kidney failure	
Yes	46 (7.1)
No	605 (92.9)

Public level of knowledge on CKD

The overall mean knowledge score regarding CKD was 14.84 ± 5.36, indicating a moderate level of knowledge across the population (Table 2). Only 24.0% of respondents demonstrated good knowledge, while 42.9% had poor knowledge. As shown in Table 3, substantial knowledge gaps were

Table 2. The overall level of knowledge of participants.

	Knowledge		
	Good	Moderate	Poor
Total scores	20–25	15–19	< 15
N = 651	156 (24%)	216 (33.2%)	279 (42.9%)

Table 3. Percentage of correct responses to individual knowledge items.

Item no.	Question	Correct response N (%)
1	A person can lead a normal life with one healthy kidney.	352 (54.1)
2	Herbal supplements are effective in treating chronic kidney disease.	142 (21.8)
3	There are certain medications that doctors can provide to slow down the worsening of chronic kidney disease.	500 (76.8)
4	The kidneys make urine.	544 (83.6)
5	The kidneys clean blood.	540 (82.9)
6	The kidneys help to keep blood sugar levels normal.	129 (19.8)
7	The kidneys help to maintain blood pressure.	470 (72.2)
8	The kidneys help to remove protein from the body.	169 (26.0)
9	The kidneys help to keep the bones healthy.	317 (48.7)
10	Blood tests are commonly used to determine the kidneys' health.	430 (66.1)
11	Urine tests are commonly used to determine the kidneys' health.	540 (82.9)
12	Stool tests are commonly used to determine the kidneys' health.	268 (41.2)
13	Blood pressure monitoring is commonly used to determine the kidneys' health.	358 (55.0)
14	Diabetes is a condition that increases the tendency to acquire chronic kidney disease.	500 (76.8)
15	Smoking is a habit that increases the tendency to acquire chronic kidney disease.	470 (72.2)
16	High blood pressure is a condition that increases the tendency to acquire chronic kidney disease.	442 (67.9)
17	Heart problems (such as heart failure or heart attack) are conditions that increase the tendency to acquire chronic kidney disease.	390 (59.9)
18	Prolonged use of painkillers is a habit that increases the tendency to acquire chronic kidney disease.	572 (87.9)
19	Obesity is a condition that increases the tendency to acquire chronic kidney disease.	444 (68.2)
20	Excess water in the body is a symptom of kidney failure.	343 (52.7)
21	Fever is a symptom of kidney failure.	307 (47.2)
22	Nausea/vomiting is a symptom of kidney failure.	294 (45.2)
23	Loss of appetite is a symptom of kidney failure.	295 (45.3)
24	Fatigue is a symptom of kidney failure.	403 (61.9)
25	Lower back pain is a symptom of kidney failure.	440 (67.6)

observed in several key areas related to CKD. Less than one-third of respondents correctly identified the kidneys' roles in regulating blood sugar (19.8%) and protein balance (26.0%), and nearly half did not recognize kidney function in maintaining bone health (48.7%). Awareness of common CKD symptoms was also limited. Less than half of participants recognized nausea or vomiting (45.2%), fever (47.2%), and loss of appetite (45.3%) as symptoms of kidney failure. These findings indicate gaps in public understanding, particularly regarding the kidneys' systemic functions and early clinical manifestations of CKD. Additionally, misconceptions persisted regarding the effectiveness of herbal supplements in treating CKD, with only 21.8% answering correctly.

Respondent characteristics and knowledge levels

Table 4 presents the chi-square analysis, which revealed significant associations between sociodemographic factors

and CKD knowledge. Females, unmarried individuals, those with higher education, and participants employed in health services or students demonstrated significantly greater knowledge (all $p < 0.05$). These results highlight gender, marital status, education, and employment as key determinants of CKD knowledge.

Public interest in CKD information

Fig. 1 illustrates the public's interest in various CKD-related topics. The majority of respondents expressed a strong interest in preventive information, including how to avoid CKD (73%), precautionary actions (70%), signs and symptoms (63%), and causes of the disease (60%). Conversely, topics such as the stages of CKD (26%) and the availability of CKD screening services (32%) received considerably less interest. This pattern highlights a public preference for practical and preventive content over clinical staging or service-based information.

Table 4. Correlation between sociodemographic data and CKD knowledge level.

		Knowledge			p-Value
		Good	Moderate	Poor	
Gender	Male	26 (12.1)	75 (34.9)	114 (53)	< 0.0001
	Female	130 (29.8)	141 (32.3)	165 (37.8)	
Marital status	Single	107 (28)	128 (33.5)	147 (38.5)	0.022
	Married	45 (17.9)	84 (33.5)	122 (48.6)	
	Divorced/widowed	4 (22.2)	4 (22.2)	10 (55.6)	
Age	18–30	112 (26.9)	137 (32.9)	168 (40.3)	0.190
	30–65	35 (28.3)	64 (33.5)	92 (48.2)	
	> 65	9 (20.9)	15 (34.9)	19 (44.2)	
State of residence	Western part	49 (24.9)	62 (31.5)	86 (43.7)	0.969
	Central part	72 (24.1)	100 (33.4)	127 (42.5)	
	Eastern part	35 (22.6)	54 (34.8)	66 (42.6)	
Education	Secondary education	26 (19.8)	40 (30.5)	65 (49.6)	< 0.0001
	Diploma/Bachelor's	88 (21.0)	157 (37.1)	177 (41.8)	
	Postgraduate	41 (42.3)	19 (19.6)	37 (38.1)	
Occupation	Unemployed	12 (20.7)	16 (27.6)	30 (51.7)	< 0.0001
	Student	47 (26.3)	63 (35.2)	69 (38.5)	
	Self-employed	6 (18.2)	6 (18.2)	21 (63.6)	
	Health service	38 (41.8)	34 (37.1)	19 (20.9)	
	Government sector	42 (17.6)	83 (34.7)	114 (47.7)	
	Private sector	11 (21.5)	14 (27.5)	26 (51.0)	
Health Insurance	Yes	100 (22.4)	157 (35.2)	189 (42.4)	0.199
	No	56 (27.3)	59 (28.8)	90 (43.9)	
Monthly income	Low	64 (25.3)	81 (32)	108 (42.7)	0.914
	Middle	44 (24.7)	60 (33.7)	74 (41.6)	
	High	48 (21.8)	75 (34.1)	97 (44.1)	
Medical condition	None	140 (25.2)	180 (32.4)	235 (42.3)	0.186
	Chronic disease	16 (16.7)	36 (31.9)	44 (41.1)	
Family history	Yes	14 (30.4)	15 (32.6)	17 (37.0)	0.529
	No	142 (23.5)	201 (33.2)	262 (43.3)	

Figure 2. Preferred methods for receiving information about CKD.

Preferred channels for receiving CKD information

Fig. 2 shows that short educational videos on social media were the most preferred source of CKD information (82%), followed by counseling from healthcare professionals (44%) and electronic brochures (41%). Traditional formats such as webinars, websites, television, and radio were far less favored, highlighting a clear preference for visual, accessible, and interactive digital content.

Public perception of the content and information delivery of current CKD educational materials

As shown in Table 5, most respondents viewed the government's CKD educational materials positively. Nearly all respondents agreed that the materials were easy to understand (99.0%), useful for prevention (99.1%), and provided clear instructions for at-risk individuals (98.3%). Perceptions of emotional sensitivity were mixed, with

Table 5. Public perceptions of the current educational materials on chronic kidney disease.

	Strongly agree	Agree	I don't know	Disagree	Strongly disagree
The educational materials on CKD that I have encountered are easy to understand.	339 (52.1)	305 (46.9)	5 (0.8)	2 (0.3)	–
The educational materials provide useful information on preventing the onset of CKD.	364 (55.9)	281 (43.2)	4 (0.6)	2 (0.3)	–
The educational materials provided instructions on how to avoid developing CKD for those at risk.	330 (50.7)	310 (47.6)	7 (1.1)	3 (0.5)	1 (0.2)
The educational materials are not sensitive to the emotions of patients with CKD.	107 (16.4)	163 (25)	148 (22.7)	190 (29.2)	43 (6.6)
The educational materials provide information that is easily understandable for people with varying levels of education.	295 (45.3)	321 (49.3)	18 (2.8)	15 (2.3)	2 (0.3)

similar proportions agreeing (35.6%) and disagreeing (35.8%), while 22.7% were uncertain. In terms of inclusivity, 94.6% agreed that the materials were understandable across different educational backgrounds.

Discussion

Indonesia, like many Asian countries, reflects the global trend of increasing chronic kidney disease (CKD) prevalence observed over recent decades (Liyanage et al. 2022). This study attempted to elucidate the current landscape of public knowledge, perceptions, and preferences concerning CKD education within the Indonesian population. The results identify both areas of adequate awareness and significant knowledge gaps. By analyzing the interplay between public understanding, sociodemographic factors, and preferred modes of information delivery, this study may offer practical insights to support the development of more targeted and effective CKD education strategies.

It was found that public knowledge of CKD remains low, with only one-fourth of respondents demonstrating a good understanding of the disease. This limited awareness represents missed opportunities for early detection and prevention and is consistent with findings from Saudi Arabia (Alobaidi 2021), Australia (Gheewala et al. 2018), and Türkiye (Gök and Şahin 2025), confirming that CKD literacy is a global concern. While most respondents recognized the kidneys' excretory role (82.9%), fewer understood their systemic functions, such as bone regulation (48.9%) and common CKD symptoms (< 50%). Limited awareness of disease consequences may reduce the perceived seriousness of CKD and delay care-seeking behavior. Moreover, although awareness of common risk factors such as diabetes and hypertension was relatively high (~70%), this knowledge did not translate into understanding of disease progression, self-management, or available treatment options. Notably, 23.2% of respondents were unaware that medications can slow CKD progression, and nearly 80% believed that herbal remedies could cure the disease. This reliance on traditional medicine, although culturally embedded, poses nephrotoxic risks if unregulated (Yang et al. 2018; Touiti et al. 2021). Addressing these misconceptions requires culturally sensitive and evidence-based communication strategies (Cipta et al. 2024).

Sociodemographic analysis revealed that female gender, single marital status, higher education, and employment in health services were significant predictors of greater CKD knowledge in Indonesia. Women's greater awareness is consistent with global trends reflecting more proactive health-seeking behaviors and engagement with health information (Thompson et al. 2016; Rata Mohan et al. 2025). This gender difference is often attributed to sociocultural roles that encourage women's caregiving responsibilities and attentiveness to health (Reddy et al. 2020). Interestingly, single participants demonstrated higher CKD knowledge, which contrasts with reports by Alobaidi and Gheewala et al. indicating lower knowledge among single individuals compared with married individuals. This discrepancy may reflect contextual differences in social support and access to health information shaped by cultural norms and family dynamics. Consistent with extensive literature, higher educational attainment was strongly associated with greater CKD knowledge (Alobaidi 2021; Albuquerque et al. 2023; Mahmoud et al. 2023), as education enhances health literacy and enables individuals to better comprehend, evaluate, and apply health information for early recognition of CKD risk factors and informed health behaviors.

Contrary to expectations, age was not significantly associated with CKD knowledge, a finding that mirrors the mixed results reported in earlier studies. Some research suggests that older adults may have greater knowledge due to cumulative health experiences (Alobaidi 2021; Younes et al. 2022), while others indicate that younger individuals are better informed, likely due to higher digital health literacy (Stanifer et al. 2016; Mahmoud et al. 2023). Taken together, these findings suggest that CKD knowledge is shaped by a combination of demographic, cultural, and informational factors. Public health promotion efforts may therefore benefit from tailoring educational strategies to the characteristics and preferences of specific populations, using culturally appropriate and accessible messaging to improve awareness and understanding of CKD.

In terms of public interest, the greatest attention was directed toward CKD prevention, followed by practical guidance on reducing risk, recognizing symptoms, and understanding disease causes. This pattern suggests that individuals are more interested in proactive strategies to maintain kidney health than in clinical or technical details. Such preferences align with global evidence showing

that people are more likely to engage with preventive health information when it is framed as personally relevant and actionable (Link et al. 2022; Li et al. 2024). For health authorities, this highlights the importance of prioritizing messages that support healthy lifestyles, risk factor control, and early awareness of warning signs.

In contrast, information about CKD staging and the availability of screening locations attracted relatively less interest. This finding is not unexpected, as disease staging may appear irrelevant to individuals who do not yet perceive themselves as ill. Similarly, limited attention to screening services may reflect practical barriers, including cost, accessibility, or mistrust of healthcare facilities (Widayanti et al. 2020; Hilmi et al. 2024; Shukla et al. 2025). Although these topics may not strongly appeal to a general audience, they remain crucial for secondary prevention. Therefore, communication strategies should balance responding to existing public interests with increasing awareness of issues that may be underestimated but are vital for reducing the CKD burden.

The mode of public education also plays an important role. Respondents expressed a strong preference for social media videos, followed by visually appealing formats such as infographics and posters, as well as personalized approaches such as one-on-one counseling with healthcare professionals. In contrast, more traditional formats, including webinars, websites, television, and radio, were less attractive. These preferences reflect broader societal shifts toward interactive, visually engaging, and easily shareable content, which has been shown to improve message reach and retention (Aida et al. 2020; Krøntoft 2021). However, the popularity of social media platforms underscores the need for health communicators to ensure accuracy, adapt messages to varying literacy levels, and counter the spread of misinformation (Jafar et al. 2023).

Public perceptions of government-provided CKD educational materials revealed both strengths and gaps. While most respondents considered the content clear, understandable, and useful across different educational backgrounds, more than one-third indicated that the information lacked emotional sensitivity. This finding suggests that although the technical clarity of the materials is strong, they may not adequately acknowledge the psychological burden of CKD. Communication that overlooks emotional aspects such as fear, anxiety, or stigma may reduce message receptivity among affected individuals. Incorporating empathetic language, patient stories, and supportive narratives could make educational materials more relatable and effective in motivating positive health behaviors (Forestier et al. 2019).

To enhance CKD education and awareness in Indonesia, future strategies should adopt culturally sensitive and evidence-based approaches. Educational content should be tailored to local beliefs and misconceptions, particularly regarding the perceived efficacy of herbal remedies and the reversibility of CKD, while maintaining scientific accuracy and credibility. Equally important is the inclusion of emotionally sensitive messaging that

integrates patient-centered narratives and empathetic language to address fear, stigma, and denial commonly associated with chronic illness.

Given the public's strong preference for digital media, social platforms and visual formats such as infographics and short videos should be leveraged to deliver clear and engaging health messages, alongside mechanisms to counter misinformation. Efforts should also prioritize inclusivity by designing outreach initiatives that consider gender, educational attainment, and occupation, particularly for populations with limited health or digital literacy. Finally, embedding CKD education within primary care and community health systems may help ensure sustainability and promote early detection, prevention, and equitable access to screening and treatment services across Indonesia.

Study limitation

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings. First, the survey relied on self-reported data, which may be subject to recall bias and social desirability bias, particularly in questions regarding CKD knowledge and perceptions. Second, the sample was collected online, potentially excluding individuals with limited internet access or lower digital literacy, particularly among older adults. This may have resulted in an overrepresentation of certain demographic groups and may limit the generalizability of the findings. Third, the study focused on public interest and perceptions at a specific point in time; therefore, longitudinal changes in awareness or behaviors could not be captured. Future research should incorporate more diverse sampling methods and qualitative approaches to explore underlying motivations and barriers in greater depth.

Conclusion

In summary, this study highlights substantial gaps in CKD awareness within the Indonesian population, particularly regarding the kidneys' systemic functions and early clinical symptoms. Misconceptions, such as reliance on herbal remedies and underrecognition of warning signs, emphasize critical shortcomings in awareness. Knowledge disparities were associated with sociodemographic factors, suggesting the need for tailored strategies.

Despite the generally clear and useful educational materials provided by the government, the public emphasized the importance of content that is emotionally sensitive and reflective of patient experiences. A strong preference emerged for preventive and practical information delivered through short social media videos rather than traditional platforms. By adopting inclusive, empathetic, and digitally driven approaches, Indonesia can strengthen public understanding and engagement, ultimately contributing to earlier detection, improved self-management, and a reduced CKD burden nationwide.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors declare to have no competing interests that could influence the work reported in this paper.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Pharmacy, Hasanuddin University (Approval No. 577/UN4.17/KEP/2024).

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

The authors declare that artificial intelligence tools were used solely to assist with language editing and readability improvement. No AI tools were used for data generation, analysis, or interpretation.

Funding

This research did not receive any specific grant from any funding agencies.

Author contributions

All authors have made substantial contributions to the conception of the study, drafting the article, and final approval of the version to be submitted. Conceptualization and Design study: SZ, YYD, and NI. Data curation and Investigation: SZ, ARM, LMS, AA, MAB, NI, and YYD. Statistical analysis: SZ. Writing – original draft preparation, review and editing the manuscript: SZ, MAB, NI and YYD. SZ, YYD, MAB, and NI prepared the manuscript for publication. All authors have read and approved the final submitted manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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